

Equilibrium and Kinetics of Pyruvate Dimerization Catalyzed by Copper(II)*

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Cu(II) catalyzes the dimerization of pyruvate via a two step mechanism: proton loss from complexed pyruvate followed by addition of another pyruvate to the complexed enolate. Solvent (H₂O) and acetate catalyzed pathways for proton loss are faster with Cu(II) than with Ni(II) or Zn(II). Below pH 4 Cu(II) forms a keto 1:1 complex with parapyruvate, but above pH 4 dinuclear enolate complexes are formed.

Parapyruvate may also be formed by decarboxylating oxaloacetate ion in the presence of Cu(II) and pyruvate.

It has been known for a long time that metal ions catalyze the rates of pyruvate dimerization.¹ The reaction is also found in biological systems, being catalyzed by metalloenzymes². Montgomery and Webb^{3,4} have found that pyruvate dimer (parapyruvate) blocks the citric acid cycle by specifically inhibiting the oxidative decarboxylation of α -keto glutarate to succinate. A series of studies being performed in our laboratories has been directed toward the elucidation of the reaction in simple metal ion systems with the hope that the results will aid an understanding of the enzymatic processes.

Results from our laboratories² have shown that the Ni(II) and Zn(II) catalyzed reactions proceed via the enolization of a metal pyruvate complex, (MP⁺), followed by an attack of another pyruvate on the complexed pyruvate enolate, (ME),

traps the intermediate,⁵

A preliminary report⁹ on the condensation of the intermediate generated by the Cu(II) catalyzed decarboxylation of oxac²⁻ to form CuD has already been presented. This paper describes the results of a detailed study of the system.

The enolate intermediate, ME, has also been proposed to be formed during the metal ion catalyzed decarboxylation of oxaloacetate,^{6,7} and it has been found that MD can be formed in high yield by decarboxylating oxac²⁻ in the presence of pyruvate, which

Experimental

In the earlier work, solutions of pyruvate dimer were obtained by catalytically dimerizing solutions of pyruvate. In this study, dimer solutions were prepared by hydrolyzing the lactone of parapyruvate, which was

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obtained from Cal Biochemical Co. Titration with NaOH yielded a purity of 97.4%. Dimer-free sodium pyruvate was obtained from Sigma Chemical Co. NaClO_4 was prepared by neutralizing reagent grade Na_2CO_3 with conc. HClO_4 , and was purified by recrystallization. The purity was determined by an ion-exchange method. A stock solution of copper chloride was prepared and standardized according to accepted methods.

A weighed quantity of parapyruvate lactone was hydrolyzed at 35°C and at pH 7.0 using a Radiometer pH stat equipped with an ABU-1 autoburet. During the course of the hydrolysis, the pH tends to decrease owing to the formation of hydrogen parapyruvate but was restored to 7.0 by the automatic addition of the titrant, 0.240 M NaOH solution. The volume of NaOH was recorded as a function of time and from this data the pseudo first order rate constant for hydrolysis was evaluated to be $1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. After hydrolysis was complete (12 hrs.) the resulting solutions of disodium parapyruvate were stored at 4° until used.

All equilibrium and kinetic measurements were run at 25° . The ionic strength was maintained at 0.5 by the addition of either NaClO_4 or KNO_3 . Determinations of pH were made with a Radiometer (Copenhagen) pH meter, M.15. The electrodes were standardized against the National Bureau of Standards phthalate buffers. Absorption measurements in the uv were performed using a Cary 14 spectrophotometer equipped with a thermostated cell holder.

data gained by the titration with standard NaOH of Cu^{2+} dimer solutions to which known amounts of HCl were added. A non-linear curve fitting technique similar to the one described by Tallman and Leussing⁵ was used to evaluate the constants. The results are given in Table I. The agreement between the theoretical curves calculated using the "best" constants and the experimentally observed data points is shown in Fig. 1. At low pH , a 1 : 1 $\text{Cu(II)}\text{-D}^{2-}$ complex was formed. There was no evidence for the formation of a 1 : 2 complex under the conditions studied ($\text{Cu(II)} > \text{D}^{2-}$). Above pH 4, inclusion of deprotonated species such as $(\text{CuDH}_{-1})_n$ and $\text{Cu}_2\text{DH}_{-1}$ was necessary to fit the data. A much better fit between observed and calculated values of pH was obtained by assuming the formation of $(\text{CuDH}_{-1})_2$ instead of CuDH_{-1} .

The formation constants of copper-pyruvate complexes (Table I) were evaluated from emf measurements using a Cu^{2+} specific ion electrode (Orion Research, Model 94-29). The concentrations of Cu^{2+} and pyruvate in these experiments were varied from $(5.0\text{-}25.0) \times 10^{-3} M$ and $(5.0\text{-}40.0) \times 10^{-3} M$, respectively, at pH 4.1-4.5.

The extinction coefficients necessary to relate rates of absorbance change at 315 nm to rates of concentration change were obtained from the results of absorbance measurements on solutions at various pH containing Cu^{2+} and dimer. At low pH , roughly pH independent absorbance values were obtained, but above pH 4, the

Figure 1. Comparison of experimental titration points and calculated titration curves for the H^+ -dimer and Cu^{2+} -dimer systems. $\mu=0.5$.

The concentrations and initial volumes are

Cu^{2+}	Parapyruvate ²⁻	HCl	Volume	Titrant
M	M	M	ml	M
● .0056	.0027	.0057	18.0	.054 (NaOH)
○ .0185	.0058	.0037	27.0	.054 (NaOH)
□ 0.00	.0078	.000	20.0	.050 (HCl)

The solid lines are the theoretical curves

The protonation constants of parapyruvate were obtained by titrating solutions of D^{2-} at known concentrations with standard HCl. The formation constants of the Cu(II) -parapyruvate complexes were obtained from

absorbance increases with increasing pH as shown in Fig. 2. Using the formation constants evaluated from pH titration data, 315 nm extinction coefficient of the various species present were calculated and are given

TABLE 1—SUMMARY OF FORMATION CONSTANTS AND EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS ($\lambda=315$ NM) OF THE COPPER (II)-PYRUVATE-PARAPYRUVATE COMPLEXES. (25°C, $\mu=0.5$)

Species	Equilibrium	log β	Extinction Coefficient ($\lambda=315$ nm)(M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)
P ⁻	—	—	22.1 ^a
HP	H ⁺ +P ⁻ ↔HP	2.105 ^a	6.24 ^a
D ²⁻	—	—	31.0
HD ¹⁺	H ⁺ +D ²⁻ ↔HD ¹⁺	3.69±0.01	25.0
H ₂ D	2H ⁺ +D ²⁻ ↔H ₂ D	5.47±0.05	11.60
CuP ¹⁺	Cu ²⁺ +P ⁻ ↔CuP ¹⁺	1.43±0.1 (Cu electrode)	58.9
CuP ₂	Cu ²⁺ +2P ⁻ ↔CuP ₂	2.57±0.1 (Cu electrode)	92.9
CuD	Cu ²⁺ +D ²⁻ ↔CuD	2.76±0.04 (pH-titration)	82.0
Cu ₂ DH ₁ ¹⁺	2Cu ²⁺ +D ²⁻ ↔Cu ₂ DH ₁ ¹⁺ +H ⁺	-0.9±0.1 (pH-titration)	1267
Cu ₂ D ₂ H ₂ ²⁺	2Cu ²⁺ +2D ²⁻ ↔Cu ₂ D ₂ H ₂ ²⁺ +2H ⁺	-1.38±0.11 (pH-titration)	2170

P⁻ = pyruvate
D²⁻ = parapyruvate

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in Table 1. Good agreement between the theoretical absorbances calculated using these values (solid lines) and the observed points is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Absorbance-pH Curves for the Cu²⁺-Parapyruvate System

$\lambda=315$ nm, path length = 1.0 cm ; $\mu=0.5$ (NaClO₄)
 O Cu_{Tot}²⁺ = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M ; Cl_{Tot}⁻ = 2.0 × 10⁻² M ;

Ac_{Tot}⁻ = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M ;

D_{Tot}²⁻ = 2.01 × 10⁻³ M

□ Cu_{Tot}²⁺ = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ; Cl_{Tot}⁻ = 1.0 × 10⁻² M ;

Ac_{Tot}⁻ = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M,

D_{Tot}²⁻ = 2.01 × 10⁻³ M

The solid lines are the theoretical curves.

A typical experiment to determine the rate of pyruvate dimerization was carried out in the following manner : Two sample solutions were freshly prepared, one containing Cu²⁺ ion and the other, sodium pyruvate. Both were similarly buffered by acetate and were adjusted to the same ionic strength, 0.5, by the addition of suitable amounts of NaClO₄. After thermal equilibration at 25°, equal volumes of the two solutions were

mixed and a portion was placed in a thermostated cell to record the absorbance changes at 315 nm. In contrast to the absorbance decreases with time as were observed with the Ni (II) and Zn(II) catalyzed reactions, absorbance increases were noted. The increases arise from the formation of the highly absorbing enolate species, Cu₂DH₁¹⁺ and Cu₂D₂H₂²⁺. The initial slope of the absorbance-time curve, $(\frac{dA_t}{dt})_{t=0}$, was determined by extrapolation to zero time. The error in the initial slope measurement is estimated to be less than 10% in most cases. The rate of increase of the total concentration of parapyruvate, $(\frac{dD_{\Sigma}}{dt})$, was obtained from the initial slopes by following the method of Tallman and Leussing.⁵

The following mass balance expressions apply to any instantaneous point on the absorption-time curve during the course of the reactions,

$$Cu_{\Sigma} = [Cu^{2+}] + [CuP^{1+}] + [CuP_2] + [CuAc^+] + [CuAc_2] + [CuD] + 2[Cu_2DH_{1-1}] + 2[Cu_2D_2H_{2-2}] \quad (4)$$

$$P_{\Sigma} = [P^{-}] + [HP] + [CuP^{1+}] + 2[CuP_2] \quad (5)$$

$$D_{\Sigma} = [D^{2-}] + [HD] + [H_2D] + [CuD] + Cu_2DH_{1-1} + 2[Cu_2D_2H_{2-2}] \quad (6)$$

$$Ac_{\Sigma} = [Ac^{-}] + [HAc] + [CuAc^+] + 2[CuAc_2] \quad (7)$$

$$P_{t \text{ or } t} = P_{\Sigma} + 2D_{\Sigma} \quad (8)$$

where at time, t, Cu_Σ is the total concentration of copper, P_Σ is the total concentration of pyruvate remaining, D_Σ is the total concentration of pyruvate dimer which has been formed and Ac_Σ is the total concentration of acetate. The absorbance at a given time, A_t is expressed as follows :

$$A_t = \epsilon_P[P^{-}] + \epsilon_D[D^{2-}] + \epsilon_{CuP}[CuP^{1+}] + \epsilon_{CuP_2}[CuP_2] + \epsilon_{CuD}[CuD] + \epsilon_{HP}[HP] + \epsilon_{HD}[HD] + \epsilon_{H_2D}[H_2D] + \epsilon_{Cu_2DH_{1-1}}[Cu_2DH_{1-1}] + \epsilon_{Cu_2D_2H_{2-2}}[Cu_2D_2H_{2-2}] \quad (9)$$

where ϵ_x is the extinction coefficient of species x. The concentrations of the complexes and protonated species in equations 4-9 are expressed in terms of the formation constants given in Table 1. On differentiating these equations with respect to time at constant hydrogen ion concentration and setting the concentrations of dimer species equal to zero at $t=0$ yields six equations which

$$\text{can be solved for, } -\frac{d[\text{Cu}^{2+}]}{dt}, \frac{d[\text{P}^-]}{dt}, \frac{d[\text{D}^{2-}]}{dt}, \frac{d[\text{Ac}^-]}{dt}, \frac{d\text{P}_\Sigma}{dt}, \text{ and } \frac{d\text{D}_\Sigma}{dt}. \quad \text{The}$$

values of $-\frac{d\text{D}_\Sigma}{dt}$ thereby obtained are given in Table 2.

Results

$\text{HO}_2\text{CC}(\text{OH})(\text{CH}_3)\text{CH}_2\text{COCO}_2\text{H}$ shows two proton ionization constants characteristic of carboxylic acids. pK_{1a} (1.78) lies in the region of that of pyruvic acid and pK_{2a} (3.69) is near that of lactic acid. These values, which have been found in this work, are in excellent agreement with those reported earlier for dimer prepared directly from pyruvate⁵.

Complex formation between parapyruvate and Cu(II) is evident from pH and absorbance changes that occur when solutions of these substances are mixed. The analysis of the pH-titration data indicates that at low pH the 1 : 1 complex, CuD, is formed. The magnitude of the formation constant of this complex (Table I) is consistent with the coordination of Cu^{2+} to either a dicarboxylate dianion such as glutarate, or lactate ion. To resolve this ambiguity the proton replacement constants have been calculated for the reactions

where L is monohydrogenparapyruvate, lactic acid and monohydrogenlactate. The values found are -0.96, -1.13 and -2.59, respectively. Comparing the Cu(II) affinities in this manner compensates for the influence of ligand basicity on the complex stability, and the relatively close agreement of the first two values suggests that the 5-membered ring, structure A, predominates over the 8 membered ring, structure B.

Above pH 4, deprotonated complexes of the type $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{D})_n^{n-}$ and $\text{Cu}_2(\text{H}_{-1}\text{D})^+$ are formed. The best fit to the data (Fig. 1) was attained for $n=2$. The possibility exists that mixtures of species with various values of n are formed, but the data do not warrant a more highly refined analysis. The absorbance increase which accompanies deprotonation above pH 4 (Fig. 2) indicates that an enolate, rather than a hydroxy complex is formed.

An enolate complex has been found to be formed between Cu(II) and the structurally similar oxaloacetate dianion⁶. The exchange constant for the reaction

$\text{Cu}_2(\text{H}_{-1}\text{oxac})_2^{2-} + 2\text{CuD} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2(\text{H}_{-1}\text{D})_2^{2-} + 2\text{Cuoxac}$ is $10^{-0.02}$, indicating that the reaction products coordinate to Cu(II) in a manner that is similar to that of the reactants. By analogy with oxac^{2-} , a structure for $\text{Cu}_2(\text{H}_{-1}\text{D})_2^{2-}$ is proposed and shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. A Possible Structure of the Dinuclear Complex, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{H}_{-1}\text{D})_2^{2-}$

The rate law for the Cu(II) catalyzed dimerization of pyruvate has been found here to have the same complex dependence on pyruvate concentration and pH as was observed for the Ni(II) and Zn(II) catalyzed reactions⁵. Buffer catalysis was also observed. Therefore, the same mechanism as proposed earlier⁵ was assumed,

where $\text{B} = \text{Ac}^-$, H_2O or P^- .

Assuming a steady state for the concentration of

CuE, the rate equation becomes

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = \frac{[Cu^{2+}][P^-](k_{1H_2O} + k_{1Ac}[Ac^-] + k_{1P}[P^-])\beta_{CuP}}{\left(\frac{k_{-1H_2O}}{k_3}\right) + \left(\frac{k_{-1HAc}}{k_2 K_{aHAc}}\right)[Ac^-] + \left(\frac{k_{-1HPP}}{k_2 K_{aHPP}}\right)[P^-][H^+] + [P^-]} \quad (10)$$

where K_{aHAc} and K_{aHPP} are the protonation constants for acetic and pyruvic acids, respectively. The formation constants reported in Table I were used to evaluate the concentrations of $[Cu^{2+}]$, $[P^-]$ and $[Ac^-]$ using the subroutine "GENDIS" developed in our laboratory¹⁰. The values of the rate constants and rate constant ratios which gave the best fit to the experimentally observed initial rates were found using a nonlinear least-squares curve fitting method. Pyruvate catalysis was found to be insignificant and hence the rate constants involving these paths were dropped from equation (10) and the remaining rate constants were adjusted to fit the data. Values of the rate constants and rate constant ratios are presented in Table 3. The theoretical initial rates calculated using these values are shown in Table 2 and good agreement between these values and the observed initial rates is evident.

other is metal ion dependent. For example, the value of k_{-1H_2O}/k_2 is smaller for Cu(II) than for Zn(II) indicating that relative to Zn(II), Cu(II) favors pyruvate addition over protonation. The corresponding ratio found for Ni(II) is not known with sufficient accuracy to place its position in this series, however, for the reaction with acetic acid the protonation/dimerization rate ratios are found to be similar for Cu(II) and Ni(II). It is also seen that, CuE acquires a proton from acetic acid at a slower rate than from the hydronium ion. This suggests that only partial proton transfer occurs in the activated complex.

Experiments were run to verify that parapyruvate could be readily generated by trapping, with pyruvate, the pyruvate enolate formed during the Cu(II) catalyzed decarboxylation of oxaloacetate, equation (3). Measure-

TABLE 2—RATES OF THE COPPER(II)-PROMOTED DIMERIZATION OF PYRUVATE (25°, μ=0.5)

Expt No.	$[Cu^{2+}]_{free} \times 10^3 M$	$[P^-]_{free} \times 10^3 M$	$[Ac^-]_{free} \times 10^3 M$	pH	$\frac{dD}{dt}_{obs} \times 10^5 M \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$\frac{dD}{dt}_{calc} \times 10^5 M \text{ sec}^{-1}$
1.	2.90	0.54	4.24	4.272	1.6	1.9
2.	3.07	0.49	2.93	3.981	1.1	1.1
3.	1.18	1.60	4.42	4.141	3.7	3.1
4.	7.22	4.09	2.82	3.845	4.0	3.5
5.	1.27	1.55	2.38	3.772	1.4	1.6
6.	1.22	1.56	3.57	3.620	1.6	1.8
7.	1.17	1.57	4.72	3.556	2.2	2.0
8.	1.32	1.52	1.46	3.521	1.0	0.93
9.	0.99	1.53	17.41	4.081	6.2	6.4
10.	0.97	1.54	18.60	4.121	7.3	6.9
11.	0.96	2.67	10.34	4.051	8.5	9.0
12.	0.35	5.21	1.69	4.351	1.5	1.5
13.	0.84	4.27	1.17	4.151	2.4	2.2
14.	1.48	3.55	6.75	3.851	1.7	2.0
15.	3.55	0.28	1.73	3.660	0.29	0.24
16.	1.83	0.91	0.97	4.102	0.79	0.74
17.	0.86	1.13	1.18	4.158	0.48	0.53

Solvent (k_{1H_2O}) and acetate (k_{1Ac}) catalyzed pathways for the enolization of complexed pyruvate are seen in Table 3 to be faster with Cu(II) than with Zn(II)^{11,12} and Ni(II)⁵. This is consistent with the fact that Cu(II) being the most electronegative of these metal ions, stabilizes intermediate pyruvate enolate more than the others. However, all of these metal ions provide considerably faster enolization paths than are reported^{12,13} for the metal ion independent reaction.

ments of the absorbances of three solutions containing Cu(II), pyruvate and parapyruvate, (A), Cu(II), pyruvate and oxac (B), and Cu(II) and pyruvate (C) were made 900 s. after mixing (the time allowed for oxac decarboxylation to be complete). The concentrations of Cu(II) and pyruvate were held constant and the parapyruvate concentration in (A) was made the same as the oxaloacetate concentration in (B). At the end of the reaction, the absorbances of solutions (A) and (B)

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THE RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE METAL ION CATALYZED DIMERIZATION OF PYRUVATE (25°)

Metal Ion	$k_{1H_2O} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$k_{1Ac} M^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$k_{1P} M^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$\frac{k_{-1H_2O}}{k_2}$	$\frac{k_{-1HAc}}{k_2}$	$\frac{k_{-1HPP}}{k_2}$
Cu(II)	$22.6 \pm 11.3 \times 10^{-4}$	0.75 ± 0.07	—	23 ± 15	3.24 ± 0.08	—
Ni(II)	$3.2 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{-4}$	(9×10^{-4})	(5×10^{-5})	$(0-180)$	3.7	62
Zn(II)	$1.15 \pm 0.19 \times 10^{-4}$	(2.6×10^{-3})	(1.6×10^{-4})	220 ± 110	(0.27)	(4.5)

A comparison of the results obtained with different metal ions, also, indicates that the tendency of the enolate intermediate to disappear along one path or the

(Table 4) are seen not only to be higher than that of the blank, (C), but are almost identical. These results are interpreted to show that the presence of the pyruvate

TABLE 4—EVIDENCE OF PARAPYRUVATE GENERATION VIA THE D. CARBOXYLATION OF OXALOACETATE IN THE PRESENCE OF PYRUVATE pH 4.10

Exp.	Cu _{init} M	Pyruvate _{init} M	Oxalac _{init} M	Parapyruvate _{init} M	A ₁₄₉ 900 secs
A.	0.025	0.108	—	.0039	2.36
B.	0.025	0.107	.0039	—	2.34
C.	0.025	0.110	—	—	2.20

in (B) caused the intermediate pyruvate enolate to be trapped, yielding an amount of parapyruvate almost equal to that initially present in (A). This result lends supporting evidence for the mechanism proposed above that pyruvate enolate is involved as an intermediate in the dimerization process.

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